

BEYOND Centre - National Observatory of Athens: Securing National and European Autonomy in Earth and Space

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Abstract

The BEYOND Centre for Earth Observation Research and Satellite Remote Sensing plays a crucial role in supporting both national and European autonomy through the provision of cutting-edge services in Earth Observation and Space Security. An overview of BEYOND Centre activity is highlighted herein together with its active involvement in both the Copernicus Emergency Management Service (CEMS) and the European Space Surveillance and Tracking (SST) Partnership. Moreover, the Centre supports informed decision making for disaster resilience with its specialized tools like FireHUB for wildfire management, FloodHUB for comprehensive flood risk assessment, GeoHUB for geophysical disaster monitoring and response, and DustHUB for advanced dust forecasting.

Keywords:

Disaster Risk Reduction – DRR, Emergency Management, Risk Assessment, Humanitarian Aid, Space Security, Space Surveillance and Tracking-SST, Hazard Modelling, Copernicus Emergency Management Service - CEMS

1. Introduction

BEYOND Centre of Excellence for Earth Observation Research and Satellite Remote Sensing is an Operational Unit of the Institute for Astronomy, Astrophysics, Space Applications and Remote Sensing (IAASARS) of the National Observatory of Athens (NOA). Poised to deliver significant services for the ultimate benefit of all European citizens, BEYOND plays a pivotal role in developing cutting-edge research and providing innovative services in crucial

Our Thematic Areas

thematic areas of security and crisis management and social growth relating to national and EU independence such as: Space Safety and Security, Disasters and Crisis Management, Citizen Safety, Humanitarian Aid, Food and Energy Security and Societal Wellbeing and Health. BEYOND Centre addresses stakeholders needs across Europe, and the neighboring Regions including Balkans, Middle East, and Africa. Leveraging large scale satellite acquisitions established at NOA's facilities, actionable information is provided on time for enhanced decision and policy making in the aforementioned areas of expertise.

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BEYOND, in the delivery of its tasks, collaborates with leading organizations, including, but not limited to, the World Meteorological Organization (WMO), the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF), the Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC) and the European Organization for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites (EUMETSAT). As key partners these institutions consistently drive together with BEYOND Centre advancements in meteorology, climate modeling, extreme weather, and man-made related hazards reduction. Furthermore, BEYOND Centre has the role of **UN-SPIDER Regional Support Office** to advance Capacity Building and services for DRR worldwide and is an active member of the CEOS Working Group on Disasters, GEO/LEO/SAR Flood Pilot “Understanding Flood Risk from Space” for the Balkan flood pilot (Evros river basin), and the **GEO Disaster Risk Reduction Working Group**. The Centre coordinates the GEO-CRADLE enabling a

mechanism that is leveraging the GEO and EuroGEO innovation in Balkans, Black Sea, Middle East, Africa and Pacific Asia areas for addressing security and DRR priorities of national civil protection and civil safety authorities.

BEYOND Centre's Role in 2021 Wildfire Crisis: Utilizing Copernicus Data for Emergency Response

In August 11th, 2021 the whole Europe went through one of the hottest summers since records began. At this same time, the scientists of BEYOND Centre monitored and informed in real time on wildfires caused by the extreme drought and unprecedented high temperatures all over Greece and Europe. We have had about 10 days of unrelenting action to analyse EU Copernicus Sentinel-1/-2/-3/5P downloaded from the Hellenic Mirror Site (CollGS) and the Copernicus Open Access Hub, both operated by BEYOND Centre to provide warnings and situational pictures of the disaster to fire controllers, authorities, and inform citizens and health authorities about the atmospheric burden due to the transfer of black carbon over the whole Mediterranean. In Greece alone, about one hundred thousand hectares of land were on fire and many communities and local economies had been seriously hit in the last ten days. And the damages in Greece was just a small portion of the enormous disasters recorded in the same period on the Sentinel images in Europe, the western coast of the US, in Siberia, South America, Central and South Africa, the Middle East. The global need for quick reliable information to support the emergency response was reflected by the systematic use of Sentinel-1/-2/-3/5P data delivered through the Hellenic Mirror Site that was installed back in 2014 at BEYOND Centre, the first Collaborative Ground Segment ever put in routine operation at European level. Since then, BEYOND's operations have grown in line with the growth in demand for Copernicus Sentinel data worldwide and a number of additional Copernicus Data Hubs which are also based at BEYOND Centre offering petabytes of satellite data in the support of European and international critical services and authorities. For example, the host of the Sentinel-5P Data Hub, which went into operation on 11 July 2018, has been publishing on average around 54,000 images per month. This is due in large part to the global interest in both the circulation of NO₂ and CO resulting from the large bushfires. In BEYOND Centre we are excited to be one of the three international nodes of the Copernicus Data Access Ecosystem that supports the uninterrupted massive publication of more than 15 million Copernicus Sentinel data on a yearly basis serving more than half a million of users over the globe.

2. BEYOND Data & IT Ecosystem: Infrastructure, Hubs, Tools

BEYOND Centre Big Data infrastructure supports acquisition, processing, storing and disseminating of EO data at scale. Data engineering best practices enable efficient ingestion and analysis of big data for any type of application herein after, ranging from disaster response to climate monitoring and scientific production. The ecosystem encompasses high-performance computing (CUDA), container-based workflows (Docker, Kubernetes), scalable geospatial databases, STAC cataloguing and EO-specific data cubes, ensuring interoperability with European and international standards. This proprietary infrastructure provides a reliable and secure foundation for EO data utilization, and ensures national and European autonomy in space-based services.

Figure 1: Infrastructure model of BEYOND, illustrating the integration of containers, data cubes, versioned code, libraries and notebooks with cloud-based infrastructure (e.g. Cloudferro). The system utilizes a SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog (STAC) and PostgreSQL for data management, enabling researchers and external collaborators to access and contribute via APIs and external data sources.

It guarantees seamless access to Sentinel and other satellite data, enabling decision-makers, public authorities and researchers to base their decisions on EO data analysis for dynamic landscape and surface monitoring, emergency response and security. BEYOND's infrastructure enables EU Space Strategy, EU Space Surveillance and Tracking (STT), the European Green Deal, and the Digital Europe Programme to foster technological sovereignty in EO-based services.

The infrastructure (a) Supports European & National Autonomy by reducing reliance on third-party EO infrastructure, (b) Improves Decision-Making through fast, AI-driven EO data processing pipelines, and (c) Enhances Security from Space with elastic infrastructure for monitoring and security related events. The key end users of the Data and IT Ecosystem are Governmental institutions & Civil Protection Authorities activating BEYOND Centre through Copernicus CEMS, the European Union SST, Security stakeholders employing EO analytics for situational awareness, Scientific and commercial EO analytics providers accessing large-scale, structured data.

The applied Research and Technology means include (a) Scalable Processing of Data: Cloud and on-premises hosted data pipelines to process vast quantities of EO imagery, (b) Docker & Kubernetes: Containerized deployment of processing workflows to enable scalable data workflows and automation, (c) Data Cubes: Multi-source EO data model for standardize time-series analysis and AI-powered analytics, (d) APIs & Databases: RESTful APIs and spatiotemporal databases (PostGIS, Open Data Cube) for efficient and structured retrieval of EO data, (e) High-Performance Computing (HPC-CUDA): Parallelized image processing pipelines for accelerated feature extraction and model inference.

The Infrastructure effectively performs (a) Scalability: Addressing the increasing requirement for high-resolution EO data storage and processing, (b) Interoperability: Seamlessly integrating

Copernicus, DIAS platforms, and European Data Spaces, (c) Algorithms and practices: Maintain state of the art practices and provide cutting edge scientific insights for EO data processing pipelines, (d) Real-time Processing: Facilitating near-real-time ingestion and dissemination of EO data for emergency response, (e) Cybersecurity & Data Protection: Implementing secure access control and attack resilience for EO-based infrastructures. The infrastructure sector of BEYOND Centre is used by key European and national authorities, research organizations, and industry players including the Copernicus Services (CDSE, Emergency Management Service, Climate

Change, Security), the National Meteorological & Civil Protection Authorities, the EU Cloud providers such as: Cloudferry, European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) & EuroHPC initiatives and Universities.

Links for more information on BEYOND Centre Infrastructure:

- <http://beyond-eocenter.eu/index.php/infrastructure>
- <http://beyond-eocenter.eu/index.php/web-services/sentinels-greekhub>
- <http://beyond-eocenter.eu/index.php/web-services/satellite-access-polar-orbit>
- <https://github.com/noa-beyond/eoProcessors>
- <https://github.com/noa-beyond/ADC>
- <https://sentinels.space.noa.gr/>
- <http://beyond-eocenter.eu/index.php/web-services/hellenic-mirror-site>

3. BEYOND Centre in the support of National and European Space Surveillance & Tracking: Enhancing Safety, Sustainability, and Risks in Space Operations

Figure 2: High-level overview of the Greek SST activities. The Greek National Operations Center for SST (GR-NOC SST), hosted by the BEYOND Centre, is responsible for the coordination of the SST activities. These include, but are not limited to, the generation of sensor plans for the Greek telescopes, the correlation of observations against space object catalogs, and the contributions to EUSST and its services.

BEYOND Centre leads the Space Surveillance and Tracking (SST) operations in Greece in the support of the European SST Partnership. It involves detecting, tracking, cataloging, and characterizing artificial objects orbiting Earth, including active satellites, defunct spacecraft, rocket bodies, and space debris. By leveraging ground-based and space-based sensors alongside advanced data processing techniques, BEYOND as the Greek National Operations Center (GR-SST NOC) for SST enables real-time monitoring of the orbital environment, supporting informed decision-making for satellite operators, policymakers, and defense entities. The role of BEYOND

and its societal and national impact in terms of security is high, considering that the number of Resident Space Objects (RSOs) orbiting Earth is continuously increasing due to the surge in satellite deployments and the accumulation of space debris.

This growing congestion increases the risk of collisions, posing a challenge to the sustainability of space operations and the continuity of space services provision, reinforcing the need for effective space surveillance and situational awareness. BEYOND as GR-NOC SST, supports the operations of the Greek observing telescopes offered by NOA, AUTH, FORTH, and NTUA. The Centre is responsible for the relevant activities at the national level, and at the EUSST level, and represents the Greek SST program in broader international collaborations, including with the United States Space Command. GR-NOC SST oversees activities that involve, but are not limited to (a) Coordinating Greek sensors for conducting space surveillance observations, (b) Processing observational data in accordance with EUSST specifications, (c) Correlating observations with known objects in space catalogs and (d) Contributing correlated results (in the form of Tracking Data Messages - TDM) to the EUSST database. As part of the Greek participation in the EUSST Partnership, GR SST-NOC actively supports the main EUSST services in collaboration with the operational centers of other EU member states that include the: Collision Avoidance (CA) – Re-entry analysis (RE) – Fragmentation Analysis (FG).

Moreover, the Center GR-NOC SST runs comprehensive analysis of state-of-the-art AI methodologies for advancing SST services and security of missions in Space. Practically, BEYOND as GR SST-NOC lays the foundation for space operations toward the autonomy in both National and EU-level, while significant benefits arise for the country as a whole, including (a) Enhancing the security of Greek satellite missions and, consequently, national security, by protecting from threats originating from or passing through space, (b) Monitoring and predicting the re-entry of space debris and other objects (e.g., spent rocket stages, ballistic missiles) of known or unknown origin, (c) Advancing space surveillance technologies (detection and tracking) by leveraging Greece's existing scientific expertise and infrastructure, (d) Integrating into emerging space markets that invest in space-related services, (e) Developing technological capabilities, specialized training and expertise, fostering a skilled workforce and advancing research in space surveillance, (f) Establishing collaborations between the Greek space industry and European and international organizations, contributing to economic growth and (g) Supporting European policies on space traffic management, security, and defense, while safeguarding the interests of the EU and its Member States.

The Strategic Partners & End users of BEYOND consist of entities such as NOA, AUTH, NTUA, FORTH, HELLENIC SPACE CENTER, Hellenic Ministry of Defense, Hellenic Ministry of Digital Governance, Hellenic Ministry of Development, EUSPA, GMV, HELLAS SAT, Libre Space Foundation, USSPACECOM, NKUA, etc.

4. BEYOND Centre in the support of the Global Copernicus Emergency Management Service for Risk and Recovery

Links for more information on CEMS Activations of BEYOND Centre:

<https://mapping.emergency.copernicus.eu/>

<https://mapping.emergency.copernicus.eu/activations/EMSN197/>

<https://mapping.emergency.copernicus.eu/activations/EMSN200/>

<https://mapping.emergency.copernicus.eu/activations/EMSN205/>

<https://mapping.emergency.copernicus.eu/activations/EMSN206/>

The Copernicus Emergency Management Service (CEMS) provides validated assessments primarily based on satellite imagery for before, during or aftermath crisis, as well as early warning services for disasters. The BEYOND Centre supports through CEMS the crisis managers, Civil Protection authorities and humanitarian aid actors dealing with natural disasters, manmade emergency situations, and humanitarian crises, as well as those involved in recovery, disaster risk

reduction and preparedness activities at global level with a high impact in as far as the national and European security and safety are concerned.

The infrastructure and excellence developed in the BEYOND Centre are actively used in Risk & Recovery Mapping, nationally and worldwide, and on a routine basis towards the effective preparedness, prevention and recovery. The research and services developed are exploiting Earth Observation and geospatial data, when and where needed, for enhanced modelling of hazards and climate related disasters, mitigation and impact assessment for an effective and timely humanitarian aid. BEYOND has been activated in the framework of the CEMS 18 times since 2024 and has successfully been undertaken to support 12 activations worldwide from which 5 in the domain of wildfires, 2 in floods, 1 volcanic unrest, 1 in drought and water management, 1 in forest degradation, 1 in illegal waste dumping, 1 in multi-hazard analysis.

To address the challenging task of hazard and disaster management worldwide, BEYOND has developed and validated a number of methodologies which exploit big EO data, expert/domain knowledge and AI techniques to model Seismic Hazards and Seismic Risks, Fire Risk Forecast, Fire Early Detection, Burn Severity Grading, Biodiversity and Food Losses, Fire Spread dynamics in time and space, Population & Assets Impact, Tsunami and Extreme Weather Disasters Forecasting, Soil Erosion and Landslides, Volcanic Eruption and Lava Flow, Ground Deformation Dynamics; Flood Delineation, Flood Depth and Flood Damage Assessment, Disruption of Transportation and Businesses. The BEYOND strategic partners in this application area are among others: The Joint Research Center of EC, the DG DEFIS, Crisis managers and Civil Protection authorities across the globe, the Humanitarian aid actors dealing involved in natural disasters, manmade emergency situations, and humanitarian crises.

5. FireHUB: A Comprehensive Wildfire Management System

FireHUB is an advanced wildfire management system that leverages free and open and big satellite data to predict, detect, monitor, and assess wildfire impacts across Greece, Southern Europe, North Africa, Balkans, Black Sea and the Middle East. A multitude of satellite systems acquired at the acquisition facilities of BEYOND Centre with varying spatial resolutions (low, medium, high) and revisit times, balancing detection speed and detail are used for the delivery of the service that in turn allows the provision to first responders of situational awareness pictures and fire hazard assessments at national level every 5 minutes.

In practice, FireHUB integrates state-of-the-art models and scientific research to deliver to civil protection agencies, defense units and the public detailed fire ignition forecasts before crisis, as well as real-time warnings and fire monitoring during crisis, and last yet importantly post-fire assessments to allow informed decision-making at every stage of disaster management. Artificial Intelligence based fire risk forecasting is of utmost importance as it utilizes cutting edge Machine Learning models to handle the task of next day detailed fire prediction for the whole Greek territory in a 500mx500m wide area. Moreover, FireHUB creates a comprehensive forest fire inventory by obtaining and fusing data from multiple data sources, including the FireHUB system of BEYOND, the NASA FIRMS¹, and the European Forest Fire Information System (EFFIS)². A complete Machine Learning (ML) workflow trains classification models on this large historical dataset, for which labels (occurrence or absence of fire) are derived and the trained classifiers are then able to provide binary predictions (fire or no-fire) along with the best use of firefighting resources in every area at risk (Apostolakis et al., 2022; Girtsou et al., 2021; Alexis et al., 2023).

¹ https://firms.modaps.eosdis.nasa.gov/active_fire/

² <https://effis.jrc.ec.europa.eu>

Figure 3 (left): Fire risk map generated on September 28, 2024 for the next day. Right – Actual wildfire perimeter in the Corinth area

Figure 4 (right): Model prediction explained in a very high-risk area. Key fire drivers include vegetation type

The BEYOND Centre advanced a 24/7 real-time fire monitoring service leverages cutting-edge technology to provide continuous, high-resolution fire detection and monitoring. Satellite METEOSAT MSG SEVIRI data are ideal to early and timely detect and monitor the fast evolving fires. Every 5 minutes, the FireHUB system detects active fires into 500 m × 500 m wide cell. The system runs prototype image processing and data classification algorithms, which have been developed with the active participation of fire brigades for incorporating their expert knowledge in the delivery of a useful fire disaster operational picture.

Another fundamental part of FIREHUB that is developed by BEYOND is known as Forest Fire Information System (FFIS)³. It provides rapid, satellite-based fire detection and burned area mapping in real-time across Europe, Balkans, North Africa, the Black Sea, and the Middle East. The system ingests and processes medium-resolution data multiple times per day from polar-orbiting satellites (EOS/Terra, EOS/Aqua, Suomi NPP, and NOAA-20), acquired in real time through the BEYOND/NOA Ground Reception Station enabling near real-time active fire detection and continuous wildfire tracking. For high-resolution burned area mapping, Sentinel-2 imagery acquired at Node 3 of Copernicus operated by BEYOND as part of the Hellenic Collaborative Ground Segment of Copernicus offers detailed assessments of fire-affected regions.

In addition, the smoke dispersion service⁴ provides high-precision calculations of smoke transport resulting from wildfires, industrial accidents, and other large-scale fires on an hourly basis at national level. Elevated smoke concentrations pose serious health risks, impacting air quality and public safety across vast regions. Last yet worth noted, the Diachronic Burnt Scar Maps (BSM) service⁵ is a fully automatic but off-line multi-sensor processing chain that takes as input satellite images of any available spatial and spectral resolution and produces precise diachronic burnt area and damage assessment products over the Greek territory for the last 42 years. It has been based on using archived USGS Landsat TM, SPOT XS, IKONOS, FORMOSAT and Sentinel-2/3 imagery over the entire Greece. The BSM is offered online and is publicly open, providing an invaluable dataset for public authorities, civil protection and scientific community.

The FireHUB system is connected to the Emergency Operations Center of the Hellenic Fire Service. Additionally, FireHUB serves multiple critical stakeholders, including the Hellenic Army for the safe planning of outdoor activities, the EC LUCAS for ensuring the safety of surveyors in the field, as well as the civil protection authorities and the general public. FireHUB is instrumental in Disaster Management operations, covering not only the entire Greek region but also the Balkans, North Africa, the Black Sea, and the Middle East.

6. FloodHUB: A Flood Risk Management and Resilience Service through Innovative Monitoring and Mapping based on Earth Observation

Floods are the most frequent disasters, affecting the largest number of people. In 2023, 164 floods were recorded worldwide, killing 7763 people, affecting 32.4 million people, and resulting in 20.4 billion USD

The FireHUB relevant link:

<http://beyond-eocenter.eu/index.php/web-services/firehub>

³ <http://ffis.beyond-eocenter.eu/>

⁴ <http://smoke.beyond-eocenter.eu/>

⁵ http://ocean.space.noa.gr/diachronic_bsm/

losses (CRED, 2023 Disasters in Number). The FloodHUB services of BEYOND Centre increase flood resilience and support the flood risk management focused on early awareness, prevention, protection and preparedness to reduce the flood risk and safeguard human health. In order to mitigate flood risk, decision-makers and civil protection authorities need reliable, timely and high-resolution information on flood risk assessment, covering all disaster management stages, particularly prevention, preparedness, response, and recovery. This need is even more crucial in highly dense urban river basins that are prone to flash floods. In this regard the FloodHUB service supports the relevant authorities in adopting effective policies and practices for better flood risk management, prevention and mitigation in near-real-time. It supports the implementation of the EU Floods Directive 2007/60/EC at national level as well as the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction, and the UN SDGs, and the UN Early Warnings for All initiatives at global level. The Near-Real-Time Floods Monitoring and Early Warning prototype service runs operationally and delivers a reliable operational awareness picture of the flood extent and depth every 5 minutes to all the relevant stakeholders across the river basin. It is built around a fully scalable and transferable modular architecture that allows the real-time ingestion and assimilation of a variety of data, depending on their availability, including, but not limited to, hydrometeorological parameters measured on the site by telemetric hydrometeorological stations, satellite data, crowdsourced information on the evolving flood, and pre-run simulations of a series of flood scenarios using validated tools as HEC-HMS & HEC-RAS in a multi-source data fusion concept. Moreover, the prototype Flood Diachronic Mapping Service is based on a fully automated system that searches, downloads and preprocesses Sentinel-1A/B SAR GRD data and then, using Machine Learning based models, automatically maps water surfaces across the river basin. It uses the Copernicus Dataspace Ecosystem as well as a set of technologies (Python scripts/libraries, ESA SNAP, OpenDataCube, GeoServer), and covers the time period since 2018. The service also includes the burnt scar mapping produced by the FireHUB Diachronic Mapping Service, in order to spatially correlate the burnt scar mapping and the flood mapping towards analyzing the impact of the wildfires on the floods.

Figure 5: The Floods Diachronic Mapping Service for the Evros River Basin

The BEYOND FloodHUB Service is used by strategic partners worldwide as [UN-SPIDER](#), the [CEOS Working Group on Disasters](#), GEO/LEO/SAR Flood Pilot “Understanding Flood Risk from Space” for the Balkan flood pilot (Evros river basin), the Civil Protection Volunteer Associations which are used

The FloodHUB relevant link:
<http://beyond-eocenter.eu/index.php/web-services/floodhub>

for the improvement of near-real-time flood monitoring, following dedicated training. Between the key stakeholders using the FloodHUB service are the Ministry of the Environment and Energy, Prefecture of Attica, Prefecture of Eastern Macedonia and Thrace, Fire Service, Civil Protection authorities at national, regional and municipal level, Civil Protection Volunteer Associations, international scientific community.

7. GeoHUB: The Global Ground Deformation Monitoring Services for Timely Geophysical Disaster Assessment and Response

Timely monitoring and mapping of ground deformation worldwide, induced by major geological hazards, such as earthquakes, volcanic activity, landslides, etc. The GeoHUB’s geoObservatory¹ service (<http://geobservatory.beyond-eocenter.eu/>) provides emergency management authorities with timely assessments of ground deformation and establishes a global observatory of differential interferograms related to major catastrophic geological events. The service provides a deeper understanding of both the mechanisms driving their occurrence and the broader tectonic activity in affected regions. The produced interferograms enable the identification of the location, extent, and intensity of occurring geological hazards and related disasters. It also provides emergency management authorities with real-time information on ground deformation, facilitating informed decision-making and the implementation of appropriate disaster response measures.

The so-called geObservatory system that supports GeoHUB, is developed by BEYOND Centre to promptly deliver to stakeholders constantly updated information on the evolution of the ground deformation in the geological hazard affected area. This information is extremely useful for the local authorities responsible for decision making for evacuation, emergency response, relief and reconstruction planning, and taking measures to protect peoples’ lives and their property. The service applies Differential SAR Interferometry (DInSAR) on Sentinel-1 SLC images, to produce pre- and co-seismic interferograms.

The GeoHUB relevant link:
<http://geobservatory.beyond-eocenter.eu/>

The GeoHUB provides timeliness and consistency in detecting and monitoring ground deformation on a global scale.

Figure 6: The geObservatory service.

8. DustHUB: Advanced Dust Forecasting Services for Environmental, Health, and Climate Impact Management

The DustHUB service in BEYOND provides timely forecasts of dust outbreaks along with their spatiotemporal and quantitative properties to local authorities and the public. The forecasting service is provided daily with a forecasting horizon of 3 days ahead. DustHUB products include the aerosol optical depth of dust, concentrations of dust at the surface as well as dry and wet depositions which make important information for a sustainable health system and solar energy ecosystem.

Figure 7.: Aerosol Optical Depth, Near Surface Dust Concentration ($\mu\text{gr}/\text{m}^3$), Dry and Wet Deposition of Dust (mg/m^2), as forecasted by DustHUB

The DustHUB relevant link:

<http://dusthub.beyond-eocenter.eu/>

The impact of the service is high. Mineral dust affects radiation and alters liquid and ice cloud properties, modifying significantly the precipitation processes. The dust particles when deposited have diverse impact. The smaller PM_{2.5} particles are

easily inhaled and deposited on the lungs and are related to human health disorders, both respiratory as well as cardiovascular. On the other end, they provide micro nutrients to the ocean and/or land ecosystems, thus affecting fishery and agriculture and food security. Desert dust is always present in North Africa, Middle East and the Mediterranean with adverse effects in various scientific and societal sectors including climate change, weather conditions, health, aviation, energy and tourism. Thus, continuous monitoring and forecasting of dust transfer as provided by BEYOND Centre through the DustHUB service assists policy makers for natural hazards and climate change mitigation activities. In the running operational version of DustHUB the forecasts are provided by using DREAM-NMM numerical model.

The meteorological core is the NCEP Nonhydrostatic Mesoscale Model on E-grid (NCEP/NMME). Surface properties are defined using the USGS global 1-km land cover data and the USDA global 1-km soil. The model is configured at $0.2^\circ \times 0.2^\circ$ resolution and includes 8 dust size bins with effective radii of 0.15, 0.25, 0.45, 0.78, 1.3, 2.2, 3.8 and 7.1 μm respectively. The service offers (a) Prediction of dust outbreaks over the Mediterranean region, (b) Estimations of expected dry and wet dust deposition, to mitigate against impacts on energy (PV panel cleaning, etc). A future challenge is to separate the mineralogical composition of dust, through which we can identify specific attributes that induce specific impacts on radiative transfer, cloud formation, ocean fertilization and human health.

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